

Digital Content Creation Skills And Job Performance Of Academics In Federal Universities In South-South, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their digital content creation skill in Federal Universities in south-south Nigeria. To achieve the aim of the study, a research questions and a corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Ex-post factor research design was used for the study. The study population consisted of all the 7,107 male and female academics in all the seven federal universities from the six South-South states. 1,393 participants representing 20% of the academic staff population was drawn from the four sampled universities in south-south zone of Nigeria using Multi-stage sampling approach (comprising stratification, purposive and simple random sampling). Digital Content Creation Skills Questionnaire (DCCSQ) and 'Job Performance of Academics questionnaire (JPAQ) were used for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using internal consistency method. The DCCSQ and JPAQ were subjected to Cronbach Alpha Analysis and the reliability indices of 0.88 and 0.80 were obtained respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study revealed that, male and female academics in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria differ in their job performance based on their digital content creation skills. It is recommended amongst others that, institutions should identify gender specific barriers, such as social expectations or time constraints which can inform policies to ensure equal opportunities for skill acquisition.

Keywords: Digital content creation search skills, , academics, operational online search skills, generic online search skills.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of information communication technologies (ICT) has remarkably affected almost every sphere of life. With ICT educational products are marketed, schools are advertised, messages are sent and received within seconds; reading materials are uploaded and downloaded for several activities like conferences, workshop, and seminars; educational settings are being transformed to where educators are expected to teach and learn using it.

The goal of information and communication technology in education as enshrined in the National Policy on Information and Communication Technology in Education by Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2019) is to meet the human capital requirements of the nation for attaining and enhancing sustainable socio-economic

development, global competitiveness as well as the individual's ability to survive in a contemporary environment using ICT. The objectives of ICT in Education are to:

- (i) facilitate the teaching and learning processes.
- (ii) promote problem-solving, critical thinking and innovative skills.
- (iii) promote life-long learning and advance knowledge.
- (iv) enhance the various teaching/learning strategies required to meet the needs of the population.
- (v) foster research and development.
- (vi) support effective and efficient education administration
- (vii) enhance universal access to information.
- (viii) widen access to education, range of instructional options and opportunities for any-where, any-time, any-pace and any-path learning, and
- (ix) promote the commercialization of indigenous inventions, products and services of ICT in education.

In the university, academics are known for teaching, research and community service. Academics, male or female make use of ICT for their service delivery (otherwise known as job performance) especially in teaching and research. Performance is the measurement of actual output or result against set goals. Job performance is the degree to which an academic or scholar can effectively combine duties (such as teaching, research and community service) (Mbon *et al.*, 2019; Odigwe *et al.*, 2020; Owan *et al.*, 2020). It is the measure of the effectiveness of academics in relation to their roles and responsibilities in their work place. Taiwo (2014) opined that Job performance is the overall expected value from employees' behaviours carried out over the course of a set period of time. Okoi and Odigwe, (2018) explained that academic staff job performance is the association between teaching features and educational success in the classroom. It could therefore be deduced that academics' performances in the universities are basically measured by their research output, quality of teaching and community services.

However, job performance is delimited to teaching and research in this study. Academics are expected to administer continuous assessment in form of class test, take home assignments, and supervise students in their research works. They are also expected to write journal articles and attend national and international conferences, seminars and workshops. Digital search skills are always on hand to enhance efficiency and effectiveness in carrying out these activities. This could help them meet their job demands and engender positive work life. Digital search skills allow quicker access to study materials through the internet. The use of online search to access journals, periodicals, magazines, inaugural lectures, conference papers could help a lecturer to grow fast on the job and in the long run; the stress that comes with teaching and research work is reduced minimally. In their service delivery, it appears that many perform their jobs effectively while some do not. Some find it difficult to update knowledge in their respective areas of specialisation. This could possibly be influenced by one's knowledge of the ICT, especially the digital research skills.

Digital research skills are the user's ability to pose a query to an information system in order to fulfill a specific request. Online Search skills are required not only for gaining access to the available information resources, but also to sift from the large quantity and optimise the most appropriate information. Online search skills are essential for effectively navigating, finding, evaluating and utilizing information on the internet. Liu and Sun (2012) defined online search skills as the cognitive and technical abilities required to use search tools to locate, assess and synthesize information from digital sources. Hock (2013) opined that online search skills encompass the methods and strategies employed to retrieve information effectively while critically evaluating the credibility and relevance of sources. In other words, online search skills are the ability to locate content online effectively and efficiently. Van Deursen *et al* (2014) posited that digital research skills include among others content creation search skills.

Content creation online search skill refers to the ability to generate, design and publish original content effectively across various digital platforms. It is the skill required to produce, edit, and distribute engaging digital content, using various tools and formats to communicate messages effectively to a target audience. With content creation skill, academics can attract, engage, and delight prospects and students, bring new visitors to their site, and ultimately, generate revenue for the department.

Content Creation is considered as the skill to produce content in different formats, platforms, and environments categories (Van Deursen *et al.*, 2014). Content creation can be seen as the process of conducting research, coming up with strategic ideas, turning those ideas into high-value collateral and then advertising them to a specific audience. Web pages, blogs, info graphics, movies and social media postings are all examples of digital content. Content writers are individuals who have specific skills in writing content that is relevant to a business or organization's target audience. Content creation skill refer to the ability to generate, design, and publish original content effectively across various digital platforms. With today's online democracy and diversity, people could easily create their own content, as well as receive news and entertainment from millions of online outlets. Academics can use their expertise and knowledge to create, deploy and modify content that is used to benefit the department and its students.

Academics can use this skill through Google's video streaming platform to advertise their teachings, generate revenue through their blogs and at the same time enhance their job performance. With the highly content sharing among people, with high electronica and virtual participation in this 'social networking era', digital skills should be mastered by one, in order to wipe out the digital inequality (Ahmad *et al.*, 2019). Online users are availed the opportunity to participate in online discussion, almost anyone can create and moderate a discussion forum, or create his/her own Web pages.

The interplay of all these digital skills could play an important role in the job performance of academics in the universities. It is arguable that some individuals experience difficulties in customizing search terms, reasoning with the search results, having a critical attitude towards the resource, and organizing the search process. The online content creation skill difficulty is sometimes debated to be more prevalent with males than females. Some empirical literature have been conducted in the subject. For instance, Wordu *et al.* (2021) found that there is a significant relationship between digital creativity and teachers' job performance in universities in Rivers State indicating that the contributions of digital creativity to academics' job performance cannot be ignored. Devon *et al.* (2015) found that creativity is gendered in nature and that the gendering of creativity contributes to gender inequality in the workplace.

From the foregoing, it appears that the evidence for specific gender differences in digital content creation skill and its effect on job performance is inconclusive although there is a widespread belief that computers and the internet are male dominated technologies. Therefore, the need to examine the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their digital content creation skill in Federal Universities in south-south Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Academics landscape is continuously evolving, today it is driven by technological advancements and changing educational demands; with these, it appears that some academics struggle to navigate the complexities of modern research environments which require not only expertise in their subject matter but also proficiency in digital tools. It appears that some academics do not know how to create online content. Moreover, some seem not to be interested in carrying out research, as they find it difficult to employ some digital content creation site in searching for relevant information. However, according to statistics from Action aid.org, women are 14% less likely than men to own a mobile phone. Moreover, 25% fewer women and girls are online compared to men and boys. In Africa, the gap is widening, with over 40% of women not able to effectively engage ICT tools for personal and professional activities. According to the UN Women.org, one out of four people that are read about in the news are women and only 27% of top management jobs in media organizations are held by women, in comparison with 73% of men.

These anomalies could be associated with lack of digital content creation skills by some academics. Some scholars argue that more male acquire more digital content creation skills than the female counterparts while others argue in favour of the female academics. These differences may influence their ability to locate relevant literature, conduct thorough research and ultimately contribute to their productivity and career advancement. Therefore, this study sought the difference in male and female academics' job performance based on their content creation online search skills in Federal Universities in south-south Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on their content creation online search skills in Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses was tested on 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on content creation online search skills in Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

METHOD

This study adopted Ex-post factor research design. It was conducted in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The South-South Nigeria is one out of the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria and it comprises of six states which are: Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta state Edo and Rivers states. The population comprised 7,107 male and female academics in all the seven federal universities from the six South-South states. This comprise of Uyo, Uyo (1202), The Federal University of Petroleum Resources Effurun located in Delta state (189), Federal University, Otuoke, Bayelsa (428), Nigerian Maritime University Okerenkoko Delta State (100), The University of Port-Harcourt (1238), University of Benin (1896), and University of Calabar (2054). The sample size of the study was 1,393 participants representing 20% of the academic staff population drawn from the four sampled universities in south- south zone of Nigeria using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Sample Size Determination Table. Multi-stage sampling approach (comprising stratification, purposive and simple random sampling) was used to select the sample of the study.

Digital Content Creation Skills Questionnaire (DRSQ) and 'Job Performance of Academics questionnaire (JPAQ)' were used for data collection. The DRSQ was divided into two sections: A and B. Section A was used to elicit response on demographic variables such as gender, while section B contained seven developed items used to collect data on the operational online search skills and generic online search skills. Similarly, the JPAQ comprised of 20 items, developed on job performance of academic's on research and teaching. Both instruments were measured on a four points rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD). To establish the internal consistency of the instruments, an inter-item approach was used. The scores obtained from 50 academics that were not part of the sample used for the study were collated and subjected to Cronbach's Alpha statistical tool. The result of the analysis was established as 0.86 for DRSQ and 0.80 for JPAQ. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for testing hypotheses was to reject the null hypotheses, if the calculated F is greater than the critical F or retain the null hypothesis if the calculated F is less than the critical F-value. In answering the research questions, the decision rule applied was 1-2.5 (Not Acquired), 2.5-4.00 (Acquired). Therefore, academics with the higher mean was considered to perform better in their job than academics with the lower mean.

RESULTS

The results of the study have been presented in Tables and explanations made based on the research questions and hypotheses of the study

Research Question One: *What is the difference in job performance of male and female academics based on content creation online search skill in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation for the difference in job performance of male and female academics, based on content creation online search skill.

Gender	Content creation Online Search skill	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	Acquired	53.53	17.97	589
	Not Acquired	45.43	15.98	406
	Total	50.22	17.63	995
Female	Acquired	34.98	7.33	215
	Not Acquired	34.65	6.94	160
	Total	34.84	7.15	375
Total	Acquired	48.57	17.84	804
	Not Acquired	42.38	14.84	566

The entries in Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics on job performance of male and female academics based on their content creation online search skill. Results as presented in the Table reveal the Mean and standard deviation for the difference in job performances of male and female academics based on content creation online search skill. It shows the job performance means of male who acquired content creation online search skills as: 53.53 and those who do not acquire with 45.43, also female who acquire content creation online search skills with job performance mean score of 34.98 and those who do not acquire with 34.84 respectively. This shows that male academics who acquired content creation online search skill performed better in their job than female academic staff in federal universities in south-South, Nigeria. The result also shows that the standard deviations of the scores for the male and female academics are above 1(17.97, 15.98, 7.33, and 6.94). Therefore male and female academics differ in their job performance based on their content creation online search skill.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on content creation online search skills in Federal Universities in south-south, Nigeria

Table 4.2: Analysis of Variance of the difference in content creation online search skill of male and female academics based on job performance

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	80264.516	3	26754.839	116.973	.000
Intercept	1886871.749	1	1886871.749	8249.496	.000
Gender	57436.127	1	57436.127	249.689	.000
content creation Online	4718.544	1	4718.544	20.630	.000
Gender * content creation Online	4015.369	1	4015.369		.000
Error	312439.297	1366	228.726		
Total	3293096.000	1370			
Corrected Total	392703.813	1369			

The result in Table 2 reveals the result of ANOVA for the significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on content creation online search skill. The result shows the F value of 17.555 with its corresponding significant value of .000 with 1 and 1366 degrees of freedom. The result is

significant; hence, the null hypothesis which claimed a no significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on content creation online search skill is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on content creation online search skills in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study for hypothesis indicates that there is a significant difference in job performance of male and female academics based on content creation Online search skills in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria. The answer to research question revealed that male and female academics in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria differ in their job performance based on their content creation online search skill. This means that male academics possess content creation online search skills more than their male counterparts. The condition therefore influences their job performance.

The differences may be attributed to the fact that Male are high in creative skills. Again, it may be due to nowadays digital technologies that are supporting the creation of one's skills and male tend to have higher propensity towards such skills creation. Also, internet trend influences male online creative skills and as such male respondents are able to attract attention online, create something new from existing online images, make changes to content that others have produced, conducting research, coming up with strategic ideas, turning those ideas into high-value collateral and then advertising them to a specific audience which are the students and as such perform better than their female counterparts. The ability in content creation skills is manifested through producing and publishing original digital content, understanding copyright and licensing issues, and engaging in collaborative online platforms which is very important in research and publications.

The findings of this study are in line with the findings by Wordu *et al.* (2021) who found that there is a significant relationship between digital creativity and teachers' job performance in universities in Rivers State indicating that the contributions of digital creativity to academics' job performance cannot be ignored. The findings of this study are also in tandem with that of Devon *et al.* (2015) whose findings revealed that creativity is gendered in nature and that the gendering of creativity contributes to gender inequality in the workplace. Specifically, men are assumed to be more creative than women, and that this phenomenon can be explained by the tendency for creativity to be associated with traditionally masculine traits as compared to stereotypically feminine traits.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that male and female academics in federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria differ in their job performance based on their content creation skills. There are considerable variations in job performance of male and female academics as a result of online search skills. Female academics should take advantage of these online search skills to enhance their performance. Based on the findings and the conclusion of the study, it is recommended that institutions should identify gender specific barriers, such as social expectations or time constraints which can inform policies to ensure equal opportunities for skill acquisition.

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